

UNDERTREES

AGROFORESTRY RESEARCH

H2020-MSCA-RISE 2019 UNDERTREES

Creating knowledge for UNDERstanding ecosystem seRvicEs of agroforEstry systems through a holistic methodological framework

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Introduction

The overarching objective of UNDERTREES is to form an international and inter-sectoral network of 15 organisations in 3 continents (Europe, Africa and South America) working on a joint research programme in the field of agroforestry (AF) and ecosystem services (ES) assessment. The participants are academic, government and enterprises that will exchange skills and knowledge to progress towards key advances in agroforestry systems’ evaluation and design, while enhancing collaborative research and innovation staff exchange across different continents. Skills and knowledge exchanges with African and South America countries, where agroforestry has a sound historical role in fostering environmental and socio-economical sustainability, will advance in agroforestry systems comprehension, with significant benefits for the European environment and society. The staff members in the project will develop new skills, will be exposed to new research environments and will have their career perspectives widened. To achieve its aim UNDERTREES identified research, training, and participatory activities at 16 study sites in 5 biogeographical areas, within three thematic areas: (1) agronomic and environmental sustainability, (2) socio-economic sustainability and (3) policy development. UNDERTREES will advance research by strengthening intersectoral cross-country collaboration, will provide training and education at academic and technical level, and will engage with local, national and international stakeholders to create shared knowledge on agroforestry ES for EU agricultural policy development.

1. Project Platform

The project platform has been created on Microsoft Teams (Figure 1), which is a communication platform offering workspace chat and videoconferencing, file storage, and application integration.

The project platform will allow the consortium:

- to store and manage data and project results
- to organize chat and video conferencing
- to share administrative documents
- to work collaboratively on documents and reports

Figure 1 - UNDERTREES project platform

2. Project Website

The UNDERTREES Project website (www.undertrees.eu) (Figure 2) has been launched in M34. It serves as a central portal into the project and its individual projects, providing information about the consortium, and research outputs. The website will be updated regularly, with sections such as the “results” section addressing UNDERTREES topics and outputs.

The aim of this approach is to maximise the visibility of the project activities to the wider public, stakeholders, policy makers and other relevant groups. The internal section, initially envisaged, to support communication amongst the project partners, has been replaced by the Teams Platform and just the section for external communication is currently available.

Figure 2 - Project Website

